

Synthesis of Some 2-[4-(2-Pyrazoline)Phenyl]-4H-1-Benzopyran-4-Ones

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The synthesis of six new hetero substituted 2-phenyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-ones starting from 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline and 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3,5-diphenyl-2-pyrazoline and 2-hydroxy, 2,4-dihydroxy and 2,4,6-trihydroxy acetophenones is described.

LITTLE attention has been paid to the synthesis of heterocyclic analogues of 2-phenyl-benzopyran-4-one although several 2-hetero benzopyran-4-ones (chromones) have been reported¹⁻⁷. The present paper is in continuation of our study on the preparation of heterocyclic analogues of the flavonoids^{8,9} and deals with the synthesis of six new 2-[4-(2-pyrazoline)phenyl]-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one derivatives (IIIa-f). The synthesis was achieved by a three step procedure.

The first step was the preparation of aroyloxyacetophenone esters (Ia-f) by the direct condensation of 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline¹⁰ and 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3,5-diphenyl-2-pyrazoline¹¹ with the appropriate hydroxyacetophenone in pyridine using POCl₃¹² which gave yields from 89-70%. These esters were subjected to the Baker-Venkataraman transformation to give the corresponding 1,3-diketones (IIa-f) which on cyclisation in acidic conditions yielded the desired

hetero substituted 2-phenyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-ones (IIIa-f).

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries in a paraffin bath and are uncorrected. The structures are supported by chemical analysis and for IIIa-f by spectral data as well. UV spectra (λ_{max} in nm) are recorded in methanol, ir spectra (ν_{max} in cm⁻¹) in KBr pellets and nmr (chemical shifts in δ ppm) in CDCl₃.

Preparation of aroyloxyacetophenone esters (Ia-f) :

General method : A solution of the hydroxyacetophenone (0.007 mole) and the required acid, 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline or 1-(4-carboxyphenyl)-3,5-diphenyl-2-pyrazoline (0.007 mole for 2-hydroxyacetophenone ; 0.021 mole for 2,4,6-trihydroxyacetophenone) in dry pyridine was cooled to about 10-15°. POCl₃ (0.4 ml per 0.007 mole of acid) was added dropwise with constant stirring while maintaining the temperature between 10-15°. After stirring at room temp. for 2 hr, the reaction mixture was treated with cold HCl solution (2N) and the product which separated was filtered, washed successively with water, cold sodium hydroxide (2%) and water and crystallised from a suitable solvent to give I (Table 1).

Compounds I and II

- | | | |
|--|-------------------------------------|--------------------|
| a) X ₁ = H | X ₂ = H | R = R ₁ |
| b) X ₁ = -OCOR ₁ | X ₂ = H | R = R ₁ |
| c) X ₁ = -OCOR ₂ | X ₂ = -OCOR ₁ | R = R ₁ |
| d) X ₁ = H | X ₂ = H | R = R ₂ |
| e) X ₁ = -OCOR ₂ | X ₂ = H | R = R ₂ |
| f) X ₁ = -OCOR ₂ | X ₂ = -OCOR ₂ | R = R ₂ |

Compounds III

- | | | |
|--------------------------|---------------------|--------------------|
| a) X ₁ ' = H | X ₂ = H | R = R ₁ |
| b) X ₁ ' = OH | X ₂ = H | R = R ₁ |
| c) X ₁ ' = OH | X ₂ = OH | R = R ₁ |
| d) X ₁ = H | X ₂ = H | R = R ₂ |
| e) X ₁ = OH | X ₂ = OH | R = R ₂ |
| f) X ₁ = OH | X ₂ = OH | R = R ₂ |

TABLE 1

Compound	m.p. °C	yield %	Mol. formula	% N Found (Calcd.)
Ia	142	89	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	7.93 (8.00)
Ib	152	82	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃	9.56 (9.66)
Ic	112	79	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₇	10.43 (10.36)
Id	207	78	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	6.51 (6.10)
Ie	225	76	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆	6.98 (7.00)
If	180	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₇	7.31 (7.20)

1,3-Diketones (IIa-f) :

General methods : A mixture of I (0.01 mole) and powdered anhydrous KOH (0.03 mole) in dry pyridine (20 ml) was stirred under anhydrous conditions for 1 hr at 45°. It was then acidified with cold dil. HCl (1*N*) and the separated solid filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous methanol to give II (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Compound	m.p. °C	yield %	Mol. formula	% N Found (Calcd.)
IIa	130	73	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	7.99 (8.00)
IIb	172	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃	9.62 (9.66)
IIc	163	89	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃	10.30 (10.36)
IId	202	72	C ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₂ O ₃	6.20 (6.10)
IIe	207	75	C ₃₃ H ₄₀ N ₂ O ₃	7.19 (7.00)
IIf	209	80	C ₃₇ H ₄₆ N ₂ O ₃	7.19 (7.20)

Preparation of 2-aryl-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-ones (IIIa-f) :

Procedure (i) for compounds (IIIa-c) : The 1,3-diketones (IIa-c) (0.001 mole) were refluxed in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) containing 1-2% (v/v) of conc. HCl for 1 hr, and then cooled and poured onto crushed ice with stirring. The solid was filtered, washed with dil. sodium bicarbonate (2*N*) followed by water. The products were recrystallised from suitable solvents.

Procedure (ii) for compounds (IIId-f) : The 1,3-diketones (IId-f) were dissolved in absolute ethanol (30 ml) containing 1% (v/v) conc. sulphuric acid. The solution was refluxed for 1 hr, cooled and poured onto crushed ice with stirring. The separated solid was filtered and washed with water.

In the case of products IIIe and f, the solid was dissolved in cold sodium hydroxide solution (2%), filtered and the filtrate neutralised with cold HCl (2*N*) to yield the desired product which was filtered and washed with water. The products were crystallised from methanol-chloroform.

2-[4-(3,5,5-Trimethyl-2-pyrazoline)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (IIIa). Orange cuboidal crystals from aqueous ethanol, dull yellow fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 168°, yield 93%. (Found : C, 75.81 ; H, 6.16 ; N, 8.54. C₂₁H₂₂N₂O₃ requires C, 75.90 ; H, 6.02 ; N, 8.43%). UV : 240, 295-310, 385 (pyrazoline). IR : 1640 (C=O) ; 1130, 1220 (C-O-C) ; 1565, 1595 (γ -pyrone ring) ; 1605 (C=N of pyrazoline) ; 1370 (gem dimethyl of pyrazoline). NMR : 1.6 (s, 6H, 5-gem dimethyl of pyrazoline), 2.1 (s, 3H, 3-methyl of pyrazoline), 2.85 (s, 2H, -CH₂- of pyrazoline), 6.8 (s, 1H, H-3 of benzopyrone), 7.35-8.4 (m, 8H, Ar-H).

7-Hydroxy-2-[4-(3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (IIIb). Deep yellow needles from methanol, green fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 259°, yield 82%. (Found : C, 72.39 ; H, 5.76 ; N, 8.13. C₂₁H₂₀N₂O₃ requires C, 72.41 ; H, 5.75 ; N, 8.05%). UV : 243, 290-305 (weak), 385 (pyrazoline). IR : 3400 (OH) ; 1680 (C=O) ; 1115, 1270 (C-O-C) ; 1550, 1600 (γ -pyrone ring) ; 1605 (C=N of pyrazoline) ; 1370 (gem dimethyl of pyrazoline).

5,7-Dihydroxy-2-[4-(3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (IIIc). Dark green needles from methanol, dark green fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 145°, yield 84%. (Found : C, 69.24 ; H, 5.51 ; N, 7.66. C₂₁H₂₀N₂O₄ requires C, 69.23 ; H, 5.49 ; N, 7.69%). UV : 262, 283-305 (v. weak), 385 (pyrazoline). IR : 3200-3350 (OH) ; 1650 (C=O) ; 1115, 1245 (C-O-C) ; 1565, 1600 broad (γ -pyrone ring) ; 1600 broad (C=N of pyrazoline) ; 1370 (gem dimethyl of pyrazoline).

2-[4-(3,5-Diphenyl-2-pyrazoline)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (III d). Yellow silky needles from methanol-chloroform, brilliant yellow fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 223°, yield 65%. (Found : C, 81.45 ; H, 4.99 ; N, 6.42. C₃₀H₂₂N₂O₃ requires C, 81.45 ; H, 4.98 ; N, 6.34%). UV : 240, 295-300, 410 (pyrazoline). IR : 1645 (C=O) ; 1130, 1220 (C-O-C) ; 1565, 1610 (γ -pyrone ring) ; 1600 (C=N of pyrazoline) ; 1105 (CH-N of pyrazoline). NMR : 3.1 (d, 2H, -CH₂- of pyrazoline), 5.25 (t, 1H, -CH-N- of pyrazoline), 6.8 (s, 1H, H-3 of benzopyrone), 7.2-8.4 (m, 18H, Ar-H).

7-Hydroxy-2-[4-(3,5-diphenyl-2-pyrazoline)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (III e). Dark orange needles from methanol-chloroform, brilliant yellow fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 285°, yield 55%. (Found : C, 78.82 ; H, 4.83 ; N, 6.12. C₃₀H₂₂N₂O₃ requires C, 78.60 ; H, 4.80 ; N, 6.11%). UV : 245, 293-300, 410 (pyrazoline). IR : 3400 (OH) ; 1680 (C=O) ; 1110, 1265 (C-O-C) ; 1555, 1600 (γ -pyrone ring) ; 1605 (pyrazoline C=N) ; 1105 (CH-N of pyrazoline).

5,7-Dihydroxy-2-[4-(3,5-diphenyl-2-pyrazoline)phenyl]-4*H*-1-benzopyran-4-one (III f). Green crystals from methanol-chloroform, orange fluorescence under uv irradiation, m.p. 158°, yield 56%. (Found : C, 75.96 ; H, 4.46 ; N, 5.93. C₃₀H₂₂N₂O₄ requires C, 75.95 ; H, 4.64 ; N, 5.91%). UV : 262, 290-305 (weak), 410 (pyrazoline). IR : 3200-3350 (OH) ; 1658 (C=O) ; 1113, 1245 (C-O-C) ; 1560, 1598 (γ -pyrone ring) ; 1600 (C=N of pyrazoline) ; 1105 (CH-N of pyrazoline).

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